

**MULTI-DISCIPLINARY APPROACH AND CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT
AS DETERMINANTS OF CAREER PREPAREDNESS AMONG PRE-
SERVICE TEACHERS IN DAVAO CITY, PHILIPPINES**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTI-DISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 49

Issue 6

Pages: 826-835

Document ID: 2025PEMJ4794

DOI: 10.70838/pemj.490608

Manuscript Accepted: 10-25-2025

Multi-Disciplinary Approach and Classroom Management as Determinants of Career Preparedness Among Pre-service Teachers in Davao City, Philippines

Janeth A. Pagsac,* Janry M. Ortega, Louie Jay R. Caloc
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The primary purpose of this study was to examine the influence of a multi-disciplinary approach and classroom management on the career preparedness of pre-service teachers in Davao City, Philippines. Findings affirm that both a multi-disciplinary approach and effective classroom management significantly predict career preparedness. The study employed a quantitative research design using the descriptive-correlational method. A simple random sampling technique was utilized to select respondents, and data were gathered through survey questionnaires. Statistical tools, including the mean and standard deviation, Pearson's correlation coefficient (r), and regression analysis, were applied to address the research objectives. Results revealed that the levels of multi-disciplinary approach, classroom management, and career preparedness among pre-service teachers were rated very high. Moreover, a significant relationship exists among the variables, with 64.8% of the variance in career preparedness explained by the multi-disciplinary approach and classroom management. These findings underscore the importance of integrating diverse disciplinary strategies and effective classroom management practices in teacher education programs to better equip pre-service teachers for their future professional roles.

Keywords: *multi-disciplinary approach, classroom management, career preparedness, pre-service teachers, Davao City, Philippines*

Introduction

Career preparedness refers to attaining and demonstrating the essential competencies that broadly prepare college graduates for a successful transition into the workplace (NACE, 2020). Rafay (2019) found that while most Arab university students were satisfied with their overall university experience, many felt that their institutions were not adequately preparing them for their future careers. Similarly, the lack of comprehensive career planning within universities has been identified as a contributing factor to such challenges (Ware & Millard, 2013).

On a national level, Geng et al. (2019) emphasized that many teachers remain unprepared to address the diverse needs of learners and to promote inclusive education—an increasingly vital aspect of contemporary teaching. These shortcomings often stem from outdated teacher education curricula that fail to meet the evolving demands of modern educational systems. Locally, Poznanski et al. (2018) reported that pre-service and beginning teachers frequently demonstrate limited understanding of classroom management, despite its central role in fostering effective teaching outcomes.

Career preparation among pre-service teachers is a socially relevant concern, as it has a profound impact on educational equity and societal development. Effective teacher preparation programs cultivate adaptability, cultural responsiveness, and evidence-based instructional strategies. Well-prepared pre-service teachers are better equipped to nurture students' social-emotional growth, promote critical thinking, and create inclusive learning environments—foundations for developing responsible and engaged citizens. Consequently, strong career preparedness not only enhances educational quality but also contributes to social cohesion, economic growth, and a more equitable society (Cochran-Smith et al., 2015).

One ongoing discussion in teacher education research concerns how a multi-disciplinary approach influences pre-service teachers' classroom management competencies and overall career readiness. While numerous studies have examined the theoretical foundations of classroom management, there remains limited empirical evidence on how these theories are effectively applied in diverse educational contexts. For instance, Baier et al. (2021) found that pre-service teachers often struggle to translate their theoretical knowledge of classroom management into real classroom practice, revealing a persistent gap between teacher education programs and actual teaching experiences.

Despite these insights, few studies have explored how a multi-disciplinary approach can bridge the theory-practice divide and enhance classroom management skills that contribute to career preparedness among pre-service teachers. Addressing this gap, the present study aims to investigate the impact of a multi-disciplinary approach and classroom management on the career preparedness of pre-service teachers in Davao City, Philippines.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to determine the influence of a multi-disciplinary approach and classroom management on the career preparedness of pre-service teachers. Specifically, it sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the level of multi-disciplinary approach among pre-service teachers?

2. What is the level of classroom management among pre-service teachers?
3. What is the level of career preparedness among pre-service teachers?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the multi-disciplinary approach and career preparedness of pre-service teachers?
5. Is there a significant relationship between classroom management and career preparedness of pre-service teachers?
6. To what extent do the multi-disciplinary approach and classroom management influence the career preparedness of pre-service teachers?

Literature Review

Multi-Disciplinary Approach

Since the world is not composed solely of discrete subjects, multi-disciplinary inquiry helps students understand their surroundings (Jolley & Ayala, 2015). By combining viewpoints, methods, and knowledge from various fields, the multi-disciplinary approach offers a comprehensive and dynamic means of addressing complex educational challenges. This strategy promotes the integration of content and insights from disciplines such as science, technology, engineering, the arts, and the humanities, thereby transcending the conventional boundaries of individual subject areas. Rather than isolating knowledge, it encourages collaboration and synthesis, allowing educators and learners to make meaningful connections between concepts and real-world issues.

To prepare students for an unpredictable and constantly evolving future, some scholars have proposed that the current educational system requires a significant transformation (Swift et al., 2024). One promising solution is the implementation of co-taught multi-disciplinary classes that integrate multiple subject areas into a single, engaging learning experience grounded in real-world contexts. This approach enables educators to present concepts through interconnected lenses, facilitating students' development of a more comprehensive understanding of a central theme or essential idea.

Teachers' and students' questionnaires and interviews were used to assess the class's efficacy. Researchers found that, after the class, students were unable to recall the material they had learned (Docktor & Mestre, 2014). Suppose the goal of the multi-disciplinary method is to integrate multiple disciplines into a single lesson or class. In that case, students should leave knowing how the material from both disciplines relates to the topic or theme. Multi-disciplinary learning activities will encourage students to actively investigate and uncover subject concepts and principles in a meaningful, authentic, and holistic way (Mård & Hilli, 2020).

While these studies highlight the benefits of multi-disciplinary learning, they also reveal challenges in ensuring the retention and deep integration of knowledge across subjects. This suggests that the effectiveness of a multi-disciplinary approach may depend on how well it is implemented and tailored to the specific context.

However, limited research examines how this approach contributes to specific teacher competencies—particularly classroom management and career preparedness—within teacher education programs. This gap highlights the need to investigate how multi-disciplinary learning strategies can be effectively leveraged to enhance pre-service teachers' readiness for professional teaching.

Classroom Management

To effectively manage their classrooms, teachers must acquire and apply classroom management techniques, just as students do. Teachers should focus on teaching both academic and soft skills, including good classroom behavior, stress management, effective group communication, and questioning and responding, in addition to academic skills (Caloc et al., 2025).

Burden (2020) emphasizes the importance of teaching students how to engage in sophisticated conversations, enabling teachers to pose thought-provoking questions and foster critical thinking. Instead of having students passively absorb knowledge from the teacher, this method encourages them to participate in meaningful two-way interactions actively.

The approaches to classroom management, instruction, and student participation of pre-service accounting teachers were examined by Kwarteng and Sappor (2021). The findings showed that pre-service teachers had greater confidence in their classroom management abilities than in their capacity to engage students and provide instruction. The results showed that pre-service instructors are pretty good at controlling student conduct in the classroom. This finding is consistent with those of Junker et al. (2021), who noted that beginner and pre-service instructors demonstrated moderate to high levels of classroom management competency.

According to Adhikari (2024), a well-organized classroom is essential for increasing students' enthusiasm for learning. Reactive and proactive methods, the creation of secure and kid-friendly learning environments, and encouraging student cooperation and teamwork are all components of effective classroom management. According to the research, providing teachers with a professional development program alone is not enough to encourage them to implement classroom management techniques in a meaningful way (Kennedy et al., 2016).

However, limited research has examined how classroom management skills, when integrated with a multi-disciplinary approach, collectively enhance the career preparedness of pre-service teachers. Addressing this gap is essential to understanding how these interrelated competencies can better equip future educators for the complex realities of the teaching profession.

Career Preparedness

For educators to work professionally, they must also be prepared for the workforce. It is their readiness and willingness to fulfill their responsibilities as educators on all levels—emotionally, intellectually, behaviorally, and so on. Preparing pre-service teachers for the teaching profession requires a high level of teacher preparedness (Luchavez & Caloc, 2024). People must be well-prepared for their jobs in terms of their mental, cognitive, physical, and behavioral preparedness. These factors could affect their ability to perform or continue in their positions (Martin-Krumm et al., 2023)

According to research, some mentors lack the necessary training to effectively mentor aspiring teachers (Altan & Salamel, 2015). As a result, their mentees receive more generic feedback on teaching strategies and do not receive tailored guidance on how to enhance their assignments and obligations. Instead of being committed to the practicum tasks, many of them opt to mentor pre-service teachers for extra compensation. A crucial function of teaching practice is to enable aspiring teachers to apply the theoretical knowledge they have learned in actual classroom settings. It has been implemented as a prerequisite for the awarding or accreditation of educational programs (Aglazor, 2017). Effective teaching practices have a significant influence on the competence of pre-service teachers in their professional activities. School teachers appear to be having difficulty understanding the best practices for providing their pupils with the best learning experience and assisting them in reaching their learning objectives (Darling-Hammond et al., 2019).

Additionally, numerous pre-service teachers reported making significant progress in understanding their lessons and gaining experience in preparation for teaching in the classroom (Keengwe, 2010). When teachers can create a precise learning aim and deliver the whole session with ease, successful results will follow (Oliver et al., 2015). This demonstrates that clear goals, combined with actual teaching practice, enable pre-service teachers to become more effective and confident in managing real classroom situations. It prepares them to handle both the content and the teaching process more successfully.

Overall, studies suggest that career preparedness among pre-service teachers is influenced by the quality of their training, mentorship, and classroom experiences. However, few investigations have explored how exposure to multi-disciplinary teaching and classroom management competence jointly shape such preparedness. This lack of integrative research justifies the present study's focus on examining how these two educational factors predict the career preparedness of pre-service teachers in Davao City, Philippines.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a non-experimental quantitative research design, specifically utilizing the descriptive-correlational method. Research design refers to the overall strategy used to integrate the various components of a study coherently and logically, ensuring that the research problem is effectively addressed. According to Kumar (2010), research design serves as a roadmap for the study's procedures, helping readers interpret results more accurately and enhancing their understanding of the data collection process.

Quantitative research examines relationships among variables to test objective theories and draw valid inferences from numerical data. As a quantitative approach, descriptive research systematically gathers and organizes information that accurately represents phenomena or behaviors within a given context (Greenhalgh et al., 2023). Meanwhile, correlational research, as explained by Krause (2018), is a non-experimental technique that explores the nature and strength of relationships between two or more variables without direct manipulation. It is employed to identify patterns, connections, or trends among variables in real-world settings.

In the context of this study, the descriptive-correlational design was deemed appropriate because it sought to describe the levels of the multi-disciplinary approach, classroom management, and career preparedness among pre-service teachers, and to determine the relationships among these variables. This design allowed the researcher to assess how variations in the multi-disciplinary approach and classroom management predict career preparedness without altering the natural conditions of the participants.

Respondents

The participants in this study were pre-service teachers formally enrolled in the College of Teacher Education for the 2024–2025 academic year. Establishing inclusion criteria for research participants or respondents is an essential step in ensuring the quality and relevance of the study. According to Ferreira and Patino (2018), inclusion refers to the basic characteristics of the target audience that researchers and investigators use to answer their research questions. This process ensures that the selected population is aligned with the study's objectives, allowing the results to be accurate, valid, and meaningful.

The inclusion criteria required that participants be currently enrolled pre-service teachers who possess relevant knowledge and exposure to the field of education. Meanwhile, the exclusion criteria were as follows: (1) respondents not enrolled in any education program offered by the College of Teacher Education, (2) those already employed as professional teachers after graduation, (3) students with no prior information or experience related to the subject being studied, and (4) individuals under the influence of alcohol during the conduct of data gathering, as this could affect the reliability of responses.

Before identifying the sampling method, it was necessary to understand the concept and rationale of sampling. Sampling is the process of selecting a particular group from a larger population to serve as a representative subset for analysis, allowing researchers to make

valid inferences about the entire population without surveying every individual (Berndt, 2020). This study employed simple random sampling, which ensured that every qualified respondent had an equal chance of being selected.

According to Burmeister and Aitken (2012), determining an appropriate sample size is a vital component of research design. Ryan (2013) emphasized that an adequately determined sample size ensures statistically significant results while optimizing the ethical and practical use of research resources. A total of 100 pre-service teachers were selected as respondents, consistent with previous research that supports this sample size for studies of similar scope and parameters.

The study examined three parameters—one dependent variable and two independent variables. As noted by Kaplan et al. (2014), a sufficiently large sample size enhances the precision of results and strengthens the generalizability of findings. Justifying the sample size is critical in empirical research to demonstrate that the collected data can effectively address the research questions, meet the study's objectives, and contribute to understanding the relationships or patterns being investigated (Lakens, 2021).

Demographic data, including age, gender, and year level, were also collected to provide a more comprehensive description of the respondents and to identify any potential trends or differences among subgroups. Furthermore, the findings of this research are intended to be presented at local, national, and international conferences to broaden academic engagement and dissemination of results.

Instrument

The researcher gathered data from the respondents using three adapted questionnaires developed for this study. The first set of questionnaires was the Multi-Disciplinary Approach Scale developed by Fitzgerald et al. (2021). The second instrument was the Classroom Management Questionnaire by Gabriz and Mackie (2023). The third tool was the Career Preparedness Inventory, adapted from Manasia et al. (2019).

Each questionnaire was carefully chosen for its relevance to the study's variables and adapted to align with the local context of pre-service teachers. The researcher ensured that the instruments were reviewed by a panel of experts to establish face and content validity, confirming that the items were appropriate, transparent, and culturally responsive to the respondents. Validity, as emphasized by Creswell and Creswell (2018), refers to the degree to which the gathered data accurately represent the intended constructs. A group of questionnaire construction specialists examined the survey tools and made minor modifications to fit the respondents' cultural and academic backgrounds.

As these instruments were adapted from previously validated studies, their reliability coefficients, as reported by the original authors, were retained. The Cronbach's alpha values were 0.88 for the Multi-Disciplinary Approach Scale, 0.91 for the Classroom Management Questionnaire, and 0.87 for the Career Preparedness Inventory, all indicating high internal consistency and reliability.

In this study, the four-point Likert scale was used, as it is one of the commonly used scales. In some instances where a specific user's opinion is essential, the 4-point scale is ideal.

Procedure

Initially, the researcher scheduled meetings with her adviser to discuss the development of the research framework. Once approved, the modified survey questionnaire was organized and presented to a panel of examiners for face validation. Additionally, the researcher obtained permission from the Dean of the College of Teacher Education to conduct the current study. Furthermore, the researcher personally distributed the questionnaire to the participants and explained the purpose of the study, ensuring that all respondents understood the voluntary nature of their participation. Before distributing the survey, informed consent was obtained from each participant, emphasizing that participation was entirely voluntary and that they could withdraw at any time without penalty or consequence.

To ensure anonymity and confidentiality, no names or identifying information were collected from the participants. The completed questionnaires were coded numerically and stored securely, accessible only to the researcher. All gathered data were used solely for academic purposes and were destroyed after the study's completion to maintain data privacy.

The collected data were then analyzed and subjected to appropriate statistical treatments. Finally, the statistical results were carefully examined and interpreted with professional caution to ensure accuracy, integrity, and objectivity in drawing significant findings, conclusions, and recommendations.

Results and Discussion

This section introduces the data and findings based on the Pre-service teachers' responses to the multi-disciplinary approach, classroom management, and career preparedness.

The very high rating of the multi-disciplinary approach indicates that this variable is consistently observed among pre-service teachers, suggesting that they actively apply and value integrative learning strategies in their academic preparation. This finding aligns with Repko et al. (2016), who asserted that students benefit from a more comprehensive learning experience when multiple disciplines are connected, resulting in deeper engagement and broader understanding. Similarly, Klausen and Mård (2023) emphasized that multi-

disciplinary learning activities foster active exploration and discovery, allowing students to understand concepts more authentically and holistically.

Table 1. *Level of Multi-Disciplinary Approach Utilized by Pre-service Teachers*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1. Collaborating with people from other discipline	3.61	.530	Very High
2. Implementing a multi-disciplinary approach in future careers	3.51	.595	Very High
3. Knowing how to include multi-disciplinary projects in a lesson plan	3.45	.592	Very High
4. Selecting appropriate strategies to develop new ideas	3.43	.640	Very High
5. Integrating hands-on activities	3.48	.594	Very High
6. Practicing incorporating real-world examples	3.54	.610	Very High
7. Planning the lessons incorporating feedback from multiple subjects	3.54	.540	Very High
8. Improving skills through a multi-disciplinary approach	3.51	.577	Very High
9. Encouraging students' collaboration in a multi-disciplinary approach	3.53	.611	Very High
10. Preparing to adapt multi-disciplinary lessons for the students' needs	3.45	.626	Very High
11. Assessing students' learning outcomes in a multiple-approach	3.49	.643	Very High
12. Understanding the concept of different disciplines in lesson planning	3.44	.625	Very High
13. Believing the multi-disciplinary approach is essential for the learners	3.50	.628	Very High
14. Being confident in planning lesson integrating multiple disciplines	3.38	.632	Very High
15. Knowing how to use multi-disciplinary teaching to address problems	3.43	.573	Very High
16. Using activities that allow students to explore various disciplines	3.46	.642	Very High
17. Creating lesson plans that incorporate multiple disciplines	3.38	.693	Very High
18. Preparing to use multi-disciplinary projects to teach students	3.42	.606	Very High
19. Confident in integrating multiple learning styles into lessons	3.45	.642	Very High
20. Having strategies to incorporate multiple perspectives in teaching	3.36	.659	Very High
Overall	3.47	.445	Very High

The item with the highest mean rating—collaborating with people from other disciplines—reflects that pre-service teachers are most confident in cooperative and cross-disciplinary engagement. This supports Borrego and Newswander (2010), who described the interdisciplinary approach as a means of dismantling traditional disciplinary barriers to foster creativity, teamwork, and innovation. Such collaboration equips future educators to work effectively within diverse educational settings, addressing complex classroom realities from multiple perspectives.

On the other hand, the item with the lowest mean rating—having strategies to incorporate multiple perspectives in teaching—suggests that while pre-service teachers recognize the value of multidisciplinary, they may lack practical strategies for integrating it into actual classroom instruction. This finding contradicts the general assumption that strong awareness directly translates into practical application. It implies a potential gap between theoretical understanding and pedagogical practice, echoing earlier findings by Thana et al. (2022) that integrating multiple disciplines requires intentional curriculum design and consistent practice.

In relation to the first research objective, which sought to describe the level of the multi-disciplinary approach among pre-service teachers, the results reveal a strong and positive perception of the approach's value. However, the identified weakness in practical integration points to an area for enhancement in teacher education programs—specifically, the inclusion of more experiential and project-based opportunities where pre-service teachers can apply multi-disciplinary strategies in simulated or real teaching contexts.

Table 2. *Level of Classroom Management of Pre-Service Teachers*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1. Encouraging student participation to foster a sense of belonging	3.63	.506	Very High
2. Using a variety of intervention methods to handle behavioral problems	3.45	.609	Very High
3. Managing classroom time efficiently to maximize student learning	3.57	.573	Very High
4. Addressing student problems	3.46	.610	Very High
5. Using rubrics in assessing performance tasks	3.46	.610	Very High
6. Maintaining a learning environment that promotes fairness and respect	3.49	.611	Very High
7. Establishing a safe and secure learning environment	3.50	.611	Very High
8. Applying a range of teaching strategies to develop critical thinking	3.51	.611	Very High
9. Providing the instructional materials appropriate for students	3.45	.657	Very High
10. Applying a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement	3.45	.657	Very High
11. Providing the pupils with instructional materials that reflect the content	3.42	.699	Very High
12. Providing the pupils with available instructional materials	3.51	.611	Very High
13. Giving praise to any students using a name	3.39	.665	Very High
14. Talking to students if something is wrong with a behavior	3.47	.577	Very High
15. Checking the performance output	3.47	.611	Very High

16. Preparing PowerPoint presentations to motivate the learners	3.51	.559	Very High
17. Providing instructional materials that promote cooperative learning	3.51	.577	Very High
18. Providing activities that ensure the participation of every learner	3.52	.577	Very High
19. Establishing the rules and sticking to it	3.45	.592	Very High
20. Planning for a variety of assessment contexts	3.49	.577	Very High
Overall	3.49	.467	Very High

The very high rating of the respondents on classroom management indicates that this variable is consistently practiced among pre-service teachers, suggesting that they possess strong awareness and application of effective classroom strategies that contribute to productive learning environments. Classroom management techniques are widely recognized as effective in enhancing student learning and promoting positive classroom climates (Hulac & Briesch, 2017). The findings support the idea that effective management is not only about maintaining order but also about creating an atmosphere conducive to engagement, participation, and inclusivity.

In this variable, the item with the highest mean rating—encouraging student participation to foster a sense of belonging—demonstrates that pre-service teachers place a high value on inclusivity and student involvement. This is consistent with Egitim and Umemiya (2023), who emphasized that a well-structured classroom fosters motivation and a sense of community among learners. Effective classroom management extends beyond behavioral control, encompassing the creation of psychologically safe, collaborative, and responsive learning environments that foster a sense of community. This finding aligns with Hulac and Briesch (2017), who asserted that management strategies that promote participation have a direct positive impact on both academic and social outcomes.

Conversely, the item with the lowest mean rating—giving praise to students using their names—although still rated very high, suggests that pre-service teachers may undervalue the nuanced role of personalized reinforcement in classroom management. This finding presents a subtle contradiction to Marzano and Marzano (2003), who found that using students' names and offering specific praise strengthens relationships, improves classroom behavior, and fosters respect. The slightly lower rating may reflect a tendency among pre-service teachers to prioritize group management techniques over individualized recognition, indicating an area where teacher training can further emphasize personalized motivational strategies.

In relation to the second research objective, which aimed to determine the level of classroom management among pre-service teachers, the results confirm that pre-service teachers generally demonstrate a high level of classroom management competence. However, the results also highlight the need to strengthen training on individualized reinforcement and emotional engagement techniques, ensuring that teachers are equally proficient in managing both group dynamics and one-on-one student interactions.

Table 3. *Level of Career Preparedness of Pre-service Teachers*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1. Achieving the learning goals to foster transformative competence	3.51	.628	Very High
2. Knowing the students' learning style	3.40	.603	Very High
3. Adapting the teaching strategy accordingly	3.48	.611	Very High
4. Applying different teaching strategies to integrate life skills	3.47	.594	Very High
5. Using different communication techniques to encourage students	3.42	.654	Very High
6. Knowing which instructional strategies to use in the lesson	3.44	.656	Very High
7. Involving all the students in class activities	3.45	.642	Very High
8. Managing classroom activities and setting clear rules	3.47	.611	Very High
9. Managing students' behavioral changes to regulate their emotions	3.43	.655	Very High
10. Contributing to students' safety within the school	3.45	.609	Very High
11. Setting clear criteria to help compare the learning outcomes of students	3.38	.599	Very High
12. Providing adequate feedback to the students to boost learning	3.41	.621	Very High
13. Communicating the results of the assessments to the students	3.42	.622	Very High
14. Assisting students in self-assessment to make them aware of their level	3.45	.592	Very High
15. Reflecting upon the teaching process to improve teaching strategies	3.49	.577	Very High
16. Getting involved in various related activities for the progress of students	3.45	.626	Very High
17. Asking for feedback from colleagues to improve teaching skills	3.50	.577	Very High
18. Continuing to improve the learning process	3.52	.577	Very High
19. Interpreting the students' learning outcomes	3.51	.559	Very High
20. Planning the teaching process based on the curricular document	3.53	.540	Very High
Overall	3.46	.462	Very High

The very high rating of the respondents on the career preparedness of pre-service teachers indicates that this variable is consistently present. This finding suggests that the respondents perceive themselves as adequately equipped with the necessary competencies to transition into the teaching profession. It aligns with the claims made by Elyashiv and Rozenberg (2024), who argue that aspiring teachers must be developed in several key areas, particularly in the critical role that their teacher educators play in helping them develop their professional competence. Such competence extends beyond pedagogical knowledge to include adaptability, reflective practice, and lifelong learning skills—attributes essential in contemporary educational contexts.

Pre-service teachers must have confidence in their ability and readiness to enter the teaching profession. Teachers are expected to adapt

to changing conditions, as many aspects of real life are constantly evolving. In support of this, Julia et al. (2020) emphasized that well-trained pre-service teachers experience a smoother transition into real classroom settings, displaying higher levels of confidence and resilience. This reinforces the idea that comprehensive teacher preparation programs have a significant influence on one's sense of professional readiness and adaptability.

In this variable, the item that has the highest mean rating given by the respondents is "planning the teaching process based on the curricular document." According to Drake and Reid (2014), incorporating curriculum-based planning into teacher education programs enhances the relationship between theory and practice, ultimately leading to teachers who are more competent, self-assured, and better prepared for the workforce. This supports the notion that aligning instructional strategies with curricular frameworks enables pre-service teachers to effectively contextualize learning objectives and apply appropriate assessment strategies that mirror authentic educational settings. Curriculum mapping helps pre-service teachers ensure their teaching practices meet educational standards by teaching them how to align defined learning outcomes with instructional content, teaching methodologies, and assessment techniques. Hence, mastery of curriculum alignment serves as a foundation for effective lesson planning and reflective teaching practice.

The item with the lowest mean rating is "setting clear criteria to help compare the learning outcomes of students." According to Brookhart (2013), encouraging student learning and teacher responsibility starts with reasonable evaluation procedures, which include the use of precise criteria. Therefore, incorporating this ability into teacher education helps create thoughtful, data-driven teachers who are better equipped to meet the diverse needs of various learners. However, the relatively lower score in this indicator may suggest that pre-service teachers still find assessment design and evaluation challenging, possibly due to limited exposure to authentic assessment contexts during their practicum. This technique also enables them to measure students' progress more precisely and make well-informed decisions about their instruction. This finding underscores the importance of teacher education programs in strengthening assessment literacy training as a vital component of career readiness.

Overall, the results of this table support the study's objective of determining the factors that contribute to career preparedness among pre-service teachers. However, the observed variation between high confidence in curriculum-based planning and lower proficiency in assessment design reveals an important pedagogical gap. This discrepancy emphasizes the need for a more balanced teacher preparation framework that integrates both instructional planning and evaluation competencies.

Table 4. *Correlation Between Variables*

Variables	Career Preparedness		
	r-value	p-value	Decision on H0
Multi-Disciplinary Approach	.783	.000	Rejected
Classroom Management	.749	.000	Rejected

A multi-disciplinary approach is related to the career preparedness of pre-service teachers, as the null hypothesis was rejected. The result highlighted by Drake and Reid (2014) is that multi-disciplinary education improves pre-service teachers' capacity to create coherent, pertinent courses that equip them for the intricacies of a real-world classroom setting. Critical theory, as outlined by Maxine Greene (1986), supports this investigation of pre-service teachers' attitudes and beliefs toward a multi-disciplinary approach. The importance of the teacher and their role in the classroom is emphasized by critical theory. Critical analysis of pre-service teachers' opinions regarding the interdisciplinary approach and their plans for instructing the increasingly diverse student bodies in their classrooms was possible.

Classroom management is also related to the career preparedness of pre-service teachers, as evidenced by the rejection of the null hypothesis. According to Marzano and Marzano's (2003) study, creating a secure and encouraging learning environment in the classroom is crucial for student progress. It is a major predictor of a teacher's readiness and long-term success in the field. The study's theoretical foundation, Deci's (2008) self-determination theory, emphasizes the importance of a teacher's behavioral authority and care in promoting pupils' achievement (Escosar & Caloc, 2024). The literature on classroom management also clarifies conceptual and factual uncertainties surrounding the idea of control, making aspiring educators more prepared for the classroom.

Table 5. *Influence of Multi-Disciplinary Approach and Classroom Management on the Career Preparedness of Pre-service Teachers*

Independent Variables	Career Preparedness				
	β Coefficient	F-value	R ²	t-value	p-value
Multi-Disciplinary Approach	.529	92.077	.648	5.131	.000
Classroom Management	.339			3.457	.001

A multi-disciplinary approach influences the career preparedness of pre-service teachers. Moran et al. (2023) claim that exposing pre-service teachers to a variety of disciplines and cooperative teaching techniques can significantly improve their career readiness by incorporating a multi-disciplinary approach into teacher education. Essential abilities, including self-efficacy, professional dedication, and adaptive expertise, are fostered by this method. Future teachers can make connections between disciplines and adapt to various classroom situations by being exposed to a broader range of topic areas, which promotes a more comprehensive understanding of the teaching and learning process. Classroom management influences the career preparedness of pre-service teachers. Zulkifli et al. (2019)

highlighted that pre-service teachers demonstrate proficiency in pedagogy and classroom management. According to the study's findings, these pre-service teachers possess the abilities and knowledge to apply instructional methodologies and manage their classes effectively. Classroom management boosts the confidence of potential teachers as they enter the workforce and prepares them to create positive learning environments. Research shows that pre-service teachers' perceptions of their confidence and readiness are positively impacted by effective classroom management. Ultimately, efficient classroom management is not only a prerequisite for effective teaching but also a crucial factor in determining a prospective teacher's efficacy and confidence.

Conclusions

The results and findings of the study served as the basis for the formulation of the following conclusions: The level of multi-disciplinary approach among pre-service teachers is very high, indicating that the integration of knowledge and skills from various disciplines is consistently practiced and valued in their teacher preparation. Moreover, the level of classroom management among pre-service teachers is also very high, indicating that they possess strong capabilities in maintaining productive learning environments and effectively managing diverse classroom dynamics.

In addition, the level of career preparedness among pre-service teachers has reached a very high descriptive level, demonstrating that they feel confident, equipped, and ready to enter the teaching profession. Overall, the study established that a multi-disciplinary approach and classroom management have a significant relationship with the career preparedness of pre-service teachers. This relationship highlights that the ability to integrate multiple disciplines and effectively manage classrooms enhances not only their instructional competence but also their adaptability and professional confidence.

These findings carry important implications for teacher education programs and policymakers. Teacher education institutions may consider strengthening their curriculum by embedding more interdisciplinary learning opportunities, authentic classroom management training, and reflective practice components. At the policy level, the results underscore the need to sustain and institutionalize teacher preparation models that emphasize holistic development—integrating pedagogical theory, classroom practice, and cross-disciplinary learning—to ensure that future educators are fully equipped to navigate the complexities of 21st-century classrooms.

References

- Adhikari, T. (2024). Enhancing quality of basic level education through demonstration method. *Triyuga Academic Journal*, 3(1), 190-207. <https://doi.org/10.3126/taj.v3i1.71980>
- Aglazor, G. (2017). The role of teaching practice in teacher education programmes: designing a framework for best practice. *Global Journal of Educational Research*, 16(2), 101. <https://doi.org/10.4314/gjedr.v16i2.4>
- Altan, M. Z., & Sağlamel, H. (2015). Student teaching from the perspectives of cooperating teachers and pupils. *Cogent Education*, 2(1), 1086291. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186x.2015.1086291>
- Baier, F., Maurer, C., Dignath, C. C., & Kunter, M. (2021). Fostering Pre-service Teachers' Theoretical Knowledge Application. *Studying with and Without Text-based Cases*.
- Berndt, A. E. (2020). Sampling methods. *Journal of Human Lactation*, 36(2), 224-226.
- Brookhart, S. M. (2013). How to create and use rubrics for formative assessment and grading. ASCD.
- Borrego, M., & Newswander, L. K. (2010). Definitions of Interdisciplinary Research: Toward Graduate-Level Interdisciplinary Learning Outcomes. *Review of Higher Education/the Review of Higher Education*, 34(1), 61–84. <https://doi.org/10.1353/rhe.2010.0006>
- Burden, P. R. (2020). *Classroom management: Creating a Successful K-12 Learning Community*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Burmeister, E., & Aitken, L. M. (2012). Sample size: How many is enough? *Australian Critical Care*, 25(4), 271–274. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aucc.2012.07.002>
- Caloc, L. J., Imperial, D., Matalam, A., & Diamante, R. (2025). Classroom behavior as a predictor of competency-based learning: A regression analysis of senior high school students. *International Journal of Multi-disciplinary Studies in Higher Education*, 2(3), 72-86. <https://doi.org/10.70847/632199>
- Cochran-Smith, M., Villegas, A. M., Abrams, L., Chavez-Moreno, L., Mills, T., & Stern, R. (2015). Critiquing teacher preparation research. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 66(2), 109–121. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022487114558268>
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. SAGE Publications, Incorporated.
- Darling-Hammond, L., Flook, L., Cook-Harvey, C., Barron, B., & Osher, D. (2019). Implications for educational practice of the science of learning and development. *Applied Developmental Science*, 24(2), 97–140. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888691.2018.1537791>

- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2008). Self-determination theory: A macrotheory of human motivation, development, and health. *Canadian Psychology/Psychologie Canadienne*, 49(3), 182–185. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0012801>
- Docktor, J. L., & Mestre, J. P. (2014b). Synthesis of discipline-based education research in physics. *Physical Review Special Topics - Physics Education Research*, 10(2). <https://doi.org/10.1103/physrevstper.10.020119>
- Drake, S. M., Kolohon, W., & Reid, J. L. (2014). *Interweaving curriculum and classroom assessment: Engaging the 21st Century Learner*. Oxford University Press, USA.
- Egitim, S., & Umemiya, Y. (2023). *Leaderful classroom pedagogy through an interdisciplinary lens: Merging Theory with Practice*. Springer Nature.
- Elyashiv, R. A., & Rozenberg, K. (2024). Fostering early career teachers' preparedness, self-efficacy and professional commitment: The role of teacher education. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 148, 104691. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2024.104691>
- Escosar, P. P. & Caloc, L. J. R. (2024). Self-regulated learning promotion and teaching practices of SHS teachers on the study skills of SHS students. *Psychology and Education: A Multi-disciplinary Journal*, 28(8): 831-839. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14413315>
- Ferreira, J. C., and Patino, C. M. (2018). Definitions and the significance of inclusion and exclusion criteria in research projects. *Journal of Pneumology in Brazil*, 84. <https://doi.org/10.1590/s180637562018000000088>
- Fitzgerald, S. L., Popa, C., Fitzgerald, C., & Vesa, A. (2021). Interdisciplinary learning for pre-service teachers. *Revista Romaneasca Pentru Educatie Multidimensionala*, 13(1Sup1). <https://doi.org/10.18662/rrem/13.1sup1/387>
- Gabriz, M. M., & Mackie, G. C. (2023). Classroom management practices of public elementary school teachers. *International Journal of Educational Management and Development Studies*.
- Geng, G., Smith, P., Black, P., Budd, Y., & Disney, L. (2019). *Reflective practice in teaching: Pre-service Teachers and the Lens of Life Experience*. Springer.
- Greene, M. (1986). In search of a critical pedagogy. *Harvard Educational Review*, 56, 427–441.
- Greenhalgh, T. M., Bidewell, J., Crisp, E., Warland, J., & Dermody, G. (2023). *Understanding Research Methods for Evidence-Based Practice in Health*, 3rd Edition. John Wiley & Sons.
- Hulac, D. M., & Briesch, A. M. (2017). *Evidence-Based Strategies for Effective Classroom Management*. Guilford Publications.
- Jolley, A., & Ayala, G. (2015). "Living with Volcanoes": Cross-Curricular teaching in the high school classroom. *Journal of Geoscience Education*, 63(4), 297–309. <https://doi.org/10.5408/14-048.1>
- Julia, J., Subarjah, H., Maulana, M., Sujana, A., Isrokatun, I., Nugraha, D., & Rachmatin, D. (2020). Readiness and competence of new teachers for career as professional teachers in primary schools. *European Journal of Educational Research*, volume–9–2020(volume–9–issue–2–april–2020), 655–673. <https://doi.org/10.12973/eu-jer.9.2.655>
- Junker, R., Gold, B., & Holodynski, M. (2021). Classroom management of pre-service and beginning teachers: From dispositions to performance. *International Journal of Modern Education Studies*, 5(2). <https://doi.org/10.51383/ijonmes.2021.137>
- Kaplan, R. M., Chambers, D. A., & Glasgow, R. E. (2014). Big data and large sample size: a cautionary note on the potential for bias. *Clinical and Translational Science*, 7(4), 342–346. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cts.12178>
- Keengwe, J. (2010). Fostering cross-cultural competence in pre-service teachers through multicultural education experiences. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 38(3), 197–204. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-010-0401-5>
- Kennedy, M. J., Hirsch, S. E., Rodgers, W. J., Bruce, A., & Lloyd, J. W. (2016). Supporting high school teachers' implementation of evidence-based classroom management practices. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 63, 47–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2016.12.009>
- Klausen, S. H., & Mård, N. (2023). *Developing a didactic framework across and beyond school subjects: Cross- and Transcurricular Teaching*. Taylor & Francis.
- Krause, M. S. (2018). Associational versus correlational research study design and data analysis. *Quality & Quantity*, 52(6), 2691–2707. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-018-0687-8>
- Kumar, R. (2010). *Research methodology: A Step-by-Step Guide for Beginners*. SAGE.
- Kwarteng, J. T., & Sappor, P. (2021). Pre-service Teachers' Self-Efficacy in Teaching Cost Accounting. *Education Research International*, 2021, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/9140161>
- Lakens, D. (2021). Sample Size Justification. *Collabra: Psychology*, 8(1), 33267. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/9d3yf>.

- Li, L. (2022). Reskilling and upskilling the future-ready workforce for industry 4.0 and beyond. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 26(5), 1697–1712. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-022-10308-y>
- Luchavez, L. J. T. & Caloc, L. J. R. (2024). Mathematical proficiency as an output of enrichment programs and pedagogical preparedness. *International Journal of Humanities, Art and Social Studies*, 9(4), 13-27. <https://airccse.com/ijhas/abstract/9424ijhas02.html>
- Manasia, L., Ianos, M. G., & Chicioeanu, T. D. (2019). Pre-Service Teacher Preparedness for Fostering Education for Sustainable Development: An Empirical analysis of central dimensions of teaching readiness. *Sustainability*, 12(1), 166. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12010166>
- Mård, N., & Hilli, C. (2020). Towards a didactic model for multi-disciplinary teaching - a didactic analysis of multi-disciplinary cases in Finnish primary schools. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 54(2), 243–258. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220272.2020.1827044>
- Martin-Krumm, C., Oger, M., & Burel, N. (2023). The quality of life of students and teachers at school, college, high school and university. *Frontiers Media SA*.
- Marzano, R. J., & Marzano, J. S. (2003). *Classroom management that works: Research-Based Strategies for Every Teacher*. ASCD.
- Moran, R. M. R., Robertson, L., Tai, C., Ward, N. A., & Price, J. (2023). Developing pre-service teachers' adaptive expertise through STEM-CT integration in professional development and residency placements. *Frontiers in Education*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2023.1267459>
- NACE (2020). *Competencies | Career and Professional Education | SUNY Buffalo State University*. (n.d.-b). <https://cape.buffalostate.edu/nace-competencies>
- Oliver, R. M., Wehby, J. H., & Nelson, J. R. (2015b). Helping teachers maintain classroom management practices using a self-monitoring checklist. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 51, 113–120. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2015.06.007>
- Poznanski, B., Hart, K. C., & Cramer, E. (2018). Are teachers ready? Pre-service teacher knowledge of classroom management and ADHD. *School Mental Health*, 10(3), 301–313. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12310-018-9259-2>
- Rafay, A. (2019). *Handbook of Research on Theory and Practice of Global Islamic Finance*. IGI Global.
- Repko, A. F., Szostak, R., & Buchberger, M. P. (2016). *Introduction to interdisciplinary Studies*. SAGE Publications.
- Ryan, T. P. (2013). *Sample size determination and power*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Swift, D., Clowes, G., Gilbert, S., & Lambert, A. (2024). Sustaining professionalism: Teachers as co-enquirers in curriculum design. *The Curriculum Journal*, 35(4), 622–636. <https://doi.org/10.1002/curj.267>
- Thana, N. P. M., Adiatma, N. T., & Ramli, N. R. B. (2022). Developing students' 21st-Century skills through a multi-disciplinary approach. *JOURNAL OF DIGITAL LEARNING AND DISTANCE EDUCATION*, 1(7), 277–283. <https://doi.org/10.56778/jdlde.v1i7.64>
- Ware, M. E., & Millard, R. J. (2013b). *Handbook on Student Development: Advising, Career Development, and Field Placement*. Routledge.
- Zulkifli, A. S., Sulaiman, N. F., & Mohamed, S. (2019). Pre-Service Teachers knowledge of classroom management. *Creative Education*, 10(12), 2548–2554. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ce.2019.1012182>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Janeth A. Pagsac

St. John Paul II College of Davao – Philippines

Janry M. Ortega

St. John Paul II College of Davao – Philippines

Louie Jay R. Caloc

St. John Paul II College of Davao – Philippines